

Acknowledgement

Authors' thanks, are due to Dr. G. S. Johar, Department of Chemistry, V.S.S.D., College, Kanpur for the interest shown by him in the work.

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Metal-Ligand Stability Constants of Chelate Compounds of 4-isonitroso-1-phenyl-3-methyl-pyrazolone-5 with Copper (II), Nickel (II), Cobalt (II) and Zinc (II)

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Manuscript received 30 August 1972; revised 4 January 1973; accepted 5 February 1973

SPECTROPHOMETRIC studies on complex formation between iron(II) and 4-isonitroso-1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone-5 (4-IPMP) and the extraction and spectrophotometric studies of copper(II) with 4-IPMP have been reported by us earlier.^{1,2} We have now determined the stability constants of some metal chelates in aqueous-ethanol medium (50% by v/v) and 0.1M KNO₃ using Calvin-Bjerrum technique as applied by Irving and Rossotti³. The ligand and its metal chelates are insoluble in water.

Experimental and Results

The 4-IPMP was prepared as shown earlier¹. The standard solution of the reagent was prepared by dissolving the required amount of reagent in pure ethanol. Metal nitrate solutions were prepared by dissolving the corresponding nitrates of analytical grade. Potassium nitrate was used to keep the ionic strength constant. Standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) solution was prepared according to the method of Allen and Low⁴. pH measurements were made with a Toshniwal pH meter.

The titrations were carried out in 50-50% (v/v) ethanol-water mixtures at 40° ± 1°. Three titrations viz., titration of (i) free nitric acid, (ii) free acid plus reagent, and (iii) free acid plus the reagent plus the metal ion, were carried out against 0.501M NaOH.

The practical proton-ligand stability constant, log ^PK^H, of the 4-IPMP has been obtained as the Bjerrum half-integral value from the formation curve. The same has also been calculated at different points using the equation :

$$\log {}^P K^H = B + \log \frac{\bar{n}_H}{1 - \bar{n}_H}$$

where *B* is the meter reading in aqueous ethanol. From the several log *K* values calculated for the system the average value was obtained as shown in Table 1. The half-integral value is found to be in good agreement with the average value.

From the metal-ligand formation curves (Fig. 1) it can be seen that the maximum values of \bar{n} for Co(II) and Zn(II) are less than 1, indicating that only 1:1

Fig. 1. Formation curves of bivalent metal complexes with 4-IPMP.

complexes are formed. For these systems log *K*₁ values have been obtained by Bjerrum half-integral method and by point-wise calculation using the equation :

$$\log K_1 = pL + \log \frac{\bar{n}}{1 - \bar{n}}$$

For the calculation of *pL* the following expression was used.

$$pL = \log \left[\frac{1 + {}^P K^H \frac{1}{\text{antilog } \bar{B}}}{T_L^\circ - \bar{n} \cdot T_M^\circ} \right]$$

where *T*_L[°] and *T*_M[°] are the initial total ligand and metal concentrations respectively.

The values of the formation constants obtained by these two methods are in good agreement (Table 1). In the Cu(II) and Ni(II) systems $\bar{n} > 1$, indicating that 1:1 and 1:2 complexes are formed. For these systems log *K*₁ and log *K*₂ values have been obtained by the least-squares method⁵. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL CHELATES WITH 4-IPMP

Method → Metal ↓	Half-integral	Point-wise calculation	
H(I)	6.40	6.39	$\log PK^H$
Cu(II)	5.10	4.75*	$\log K_1$
	4.00	4.04*	$\log K_2$
	9.10	8.79*	$\log \beta_2$
Ni(II)	4.30	4.32*	$\log K_1$
	3.40	3.33*	$\log K_2$
	7.70	7.65*	$\log \beta_2$
Co(II)	3.50	3.45	$\log K_1$
Zn(II)	3.13	3.09	$\log K_1$

* Method of Least Squares.

The data in Table I show that the order of stability is $\text{Cu} > \text{Ni} > \text{Co} > \text{Zn}$. This is in agreement with Irving-Williams order⁶.

Acknowledgement

Authors' grateful thanks are due to Prof. Dr. R. D. Patel, Head, Department of Chemistry, for constant encouragement in carrying out this work.

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The Study of Mixed Pyrochlores

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Manuscript received 30 August 1972; accepted 6 February 1973

COMPOUNDS with the pyrochlore structure having formula $\text{A}_2\text{B}_2\text{O}_7$ have been reported by workers.¹⁻⁶ In the present studies two new mixed pyrochlores have been studied by X-ray powder diffraction and infrared technique.

In the cubic pyrochlore structure the large A cations are coordinated by eight oxygen ions and the smaller B cations are octahedrally surrounded by six oxygen ions.

The procedure adopted in the preparation of the samples is the same as reported in the previous communication.⁷ The X-ray patterns were taken on philips X-ray diffractometer using Cu $K\alpha$ radiation filtered through nickel. The infrared spectra were recorded from 250–800 cm^{-1} using KBr pellets. The results of X-ray analysis are given in Table 1.

TABLE I

Formula	Colour	Radius ratio rX/rY	Phases present
YSmTi ₂ O ₇	white	1.35	Pyrochlore ($a = 10.121 \pm .005 \text{ \AA}$)
YDyTi ₂ O ₇	white	1.24	Pyrochlore ($a = 10.050 \pm .005 \text{ \AA}$)
YNdTi ₂ O ₇	pale bluish	1.44	Pyrochlore ($a = 10.140 \pm .005 \text{ \AA}$) + Nd ₂ Ti ₂ O ₇)

From Table 1. it is observed that YSmTi₂O₇ and YDyTi₂O₇ have pyrochlore structures while YNdTi₂O₇ showed two phases, major pyrochlore phase and minor noncubic Nd₂Ti₂O₇ phase. Recently Knop⁶ have reported the stability region extending from Ahrens radius ratio $r(\text{A}^{3+}) : r(\text{Ti}^{4+})$, of about 1.22 to 1.50 for pyrochlore titanates. Though YNdTi₂O₇ ($rX/rY = 1.44$) is within the stability limit reported by Knop *et al.*⁶ for pyrochlore titanates, it did not show only pyrochlore phase. (The heating temperature was 1350° for 5 hr).

The infra-red spectrum of YSmYi₂O₇ was quite identical with the spectra of pyrochlore titanates reported by Knop⁶. The main feature of the YSmTi₂O₇ spectrum in the region 300–700 cm^{-1} , is a strong band with a wide flat maximum exhibiting shallow fine structure peaks at 276, 380, 430, 445 and 540.

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